

“MODERN MATHS” AND “PROJECT MATHS”: POLAR OPPOSITES OR MIRROR IMAGES?

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The “Project Maths” curriculum initiative, affecting post-primary mathematics education in Ireland from 2008 and fully established only by 2018, has attracted much attention. Unlike reforms in the preceding 30 years, it involved a fundamental critique of the nature and purpose of mathematics education and addressed both junior cycle and senior cycle at the same time. The resulting curriculum has been contrasted with that reflecting so-called “Modern Maths”, introduced in Ireland in the 1960s and 1970s. However, in this paper, it is argued that the two initiatives (while differing in some key respects) had many features in common, and that the vision and excitement round the earlier development has been lost – and its purpose misunderstood – over the intervening years. As well as aiming to re-establish the historical narrative, the paper addresses the issue of faithfully implementing curricula, especially those infused by a vision of their subject area not necessarily shared by teachers.

INTRODUCTION

The decade from 2008 to 2018 has been one of notable activity in Irish mathematics education. A major curriculum initiative at post-primary level, “Project Maths”, was introduced at the beginning of that period, and was fully established – in the sense that all students completing post-primary education experienced it in its final form from First Year through to Sixth Year – only in 2018. The initiative has been the subject of lively debate. In discussions, the style of curriculum introduced by Project Maths is often contrasted with an earlier movement, “Modern Maths” (“Modern Mathematics”, or, in America, “New Math”), which affected Irish mathematics education from the 1960s. In this paper, it is argued that *the perception of contrast is based in part on a serious misunderstanding of the aims and legacy of the Modern Maths period, and that such misunderstanding has masked some of the difficulties in making radical changes to the culture of mathematics education in Ireland.*

Two reasons can be given for presenting such an argument now. First, the recent initiation of further junior cycle reform provides a natural starting point for reflection on Project Maths and on the changes that it has brought about. While this paper does not offer a critique of the project, it raises issues that may be relevant to such a critique. Secondly, with the passage of time, the number of people who can recall the Modern Maths movement is decreasing, and first-hand recollections are in danger of being lost. The author was a school teacher in the Modern Maths era, and subsequently worked with international studies of curriculum and attainment dealing with issues that it raised; hence, the paper has the strengths – and the limitations – of presenting documentary evidence framed by relevant personal experience.

In the paper, the context and frameworks that underpin the discussion are outlined. The story of the Modern Maths period is then told in some detail; the era that followed is also described, and a short account is given of the Project Maths initiative. Comparisons and contrasts are identified and conclusions drawn, noting implications for the future.

CONTEXT AND FRAMEWORKS

The context is provided by a brief overview of international trends in mathematics education over the fifty years from around 1960. While there are differences in emphasis and timing between countries, a typical pattern involves four periods: first, the introduction of “Modern” mathematics (identified here by the initial capital letter, and described more fully below); secondly, a swing back towards emphasis on basic computational skills; thirdly, a reaction to this, involving priority given to problem solving; and finally, a focus also on contexts and applications in what are known as “Reform” curricula (Herrero & Owens, 2001; Lampiselkä, Ahtee, Pehkonen, Meri, & Eloranta, 2007; Walmsley, 2007). This simple outline conceals some variations. A more nuanced analysis of the theories affecting the first two periods in the years up to 1980, as regards both curriculum content and pedagogy, is provided by Howson, Keitel and Kilpatrick (1981). By 1990, a move away from domination by any specific theory is noted in Howson’s (1991) study of the content of (mainly) European curricula. The subsequent emergence of Reform curricula again reflects theoretical underpinnings: in particular, social constructivist beliefs about learning, and an understanding of mathematics itself as a dynamic subject built up by human beings rather than as a body of knowledge that is already existing and close to absolute truth (Ernest, 2014). Similarities and contrasts between the Modern Maths and the Reform periods in the USA have already been identified (Herrero & Owens, 2001; Walmsley, 2007); the present paper addresses the issues in an Irish context. Overall, the four periods provide a historical framework for the paper.

A second framework is drawn from the large-scale studies of mathematics education conducted by the International Association for the Evaluation of Educational Achievement (IEA) (<http://timssandpirls.bc.edu>) and by the Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) via its Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) (<http://www.oecd.org/pisa>). The IEA’s Second International Mathematics Study (SIMS), a cross-national study of curriculum and achievement carried out in the 1980s, introduced the now familiar three-level model of curriculum: *intended* (decreed typically by a State department of education or equivalent), *implemented* (taught by teachers in school classrooms), and *attained* (learnt by students). Originally applying to mathematical content, the model was developed into a 3×3 grid, used by SIMS and in a slightly expanded version by PISA (Travers & Westbury, 1989; Shiel, Cosgrove, Sofroniou, & Kelly, 2001). The rows indicated the three levels, while the columns represented *content* (the original version), *contexts* (such as the structure of education systems and school and classroom conditions) and *antecedents* (representing factors such as level of economic development and characteristics of participating teachers and students). Over time, the model has been refined in different ways, especially with regard to influences on the implemented (or “enacted”) curriculum: for example, including textbooks and examinations explicitly as important determinants of teaching, and taking account of teacher and student knowledge, beliefs and practices (Thompson & Usiskin, 2014). Criticisms of such models include the fact that they may seem to view teachers as agents who should carry out official intentions faithfully, rather than as professionals with their own agency (Looney, 2014). In this short paper, reference is made chiefly to the original model dealing with content, though bearing other aspects in mind, and there is no intention to cast teachers in a passive role.

THE MODERN MATHS STORY

The origins of the 1960s curriculum changes in Ireland are not readily available in official documents. However, evidence does exist, notably in the papers written in the 1970s and early 1980s for Ireland's participation in SIMS. The Irish National Committee for SIMS included an inspector from the Department of Education and several teachers who had taught the new courses in the 1960s, hence providing well-informed insights into the developments. The present author was the research coordinator. An article based on one of the Committee's major submissions to the curriculum element of SIMS (Oldham, 1980) is the source of material not otherwise referenced in this section.

The reforms of the 1960s had their roots in the 1950s; they reflected the international movement towards Modern mathematics that aimed to bring school subject-matter more in line with the subject as developed at third level – in particular emphasising mathematics as the *study of structures* and presenting it via uniform and precise language (Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD), 1961; Fey, 2016; Howson et al., 1981). The third-level focus was mainly on content. However, at school level the changes were also intended to enhance *learning for understanding*: emphasising the relationships between mathematical concepts and topics, and in some cases focusing on concept development via discovery or from intuitive starting points (OECD, 1961; Howson et al., 1981; Walmsley, 2007). In Ireland, the revised curricula of the 1960s and early 1970s resulted from conscious engagement with these trends. The aim was not only to update mathematical content, but also – an important point for this paper – to counteract a perceived over-emphasis on procedural fluency at the expense of conceptual understanding.

The changes were phased in over a decade. The first revisions were made to the Leaving Certificate (senior cycle) courses in 1964 for examination from 1966; they brought in typically Modern elementary material – sets, relations, functions as special relations, and number bases other than ten. Changes not associated with the Modern movement also took place, introducing statistics, probability at what is now called Higher level, and differential calculus and coordinate geometry at what is now called Ordinary level. In 1966, revised Intermediate Certificate (junior cycle) courses were initiated, for examination from 1969; they included the elementary Modern material and statistics, together with informal transformation geometry alongside the familiar deductive treatment in the style of Euclid. This necessitated a further revision of the Leaving Certificate courses for 1969. A major feature at Higher level was the introduction of matrices and (as an option) groups, together with enhanced treatment of complex numbers and vectors, giving the study of *algebraic structures* a very prominent place. The Ordinary course likewise featured algebraic structures: complex numbers, vectors, and groups (again as an option), and a more formal study of transformation geometry. It also included some integration. The final revision of the period, in 1973, was to the Intermediate courses; a major feature was the replacement of the hybrid approach to geometry by a unified Modern system based on sets and transformations. That curriculum was the first to contain a “Preamble” setting out objectives. Notably, these referred to *understanding* of concepts and logical structure and of the nature of proof; *discovery of generalisations*; and *awareness of applications from everyday life* (Department of Education, n.d.).

The early developments were highlighted in the media and were generally greeted with excitement. However, they preceded much of the growth in post-primary school participation that was a feature of the late 1960s and 1970s, changing the nature of the target population. The curricula catered poorly for less-academic learners and those unready for abstractions, and this led in time to considerable disenchantment. When revised Leaving Certificate courses were introduced in 1976 (to build on the 1973 Intermediate curriculum), the Ordinary course was made less abstract, in particular by excluding groups and integration. Overall, the revision marked the beginning of a move away from Modern material, for instance changing the placement of options in the Higher course so that the strong focus on algebraic structure could be avoided (Department of Education, n.d.).

Description so far has focused on the *intended* level. *Implementation* in the classroom was supported initially by (for the time) extensive courses for teachers, introducing them to the new content. However, it can be argued that these courses did not address the underlying philosophy of the Modern movement; that teachers' beliefs about mathematics and mathematics education were not necessarily in accord with the Modern philosophy; and that – partly as a result – the intentions were never fully implemented in the majority of classrooms. In terms of *attainment*, dissatisfaction with the level of procedural fluency displayed by students developed over time. The 1973 and 1976 revisions placed some additional emphasis on this aspect by reflecting it more strongly in the examination papers, though without embracing the spirit of the back-to-the-basics movement that was dominant in the USA [1].

BETWEEN THE MODERN MATHS AND PROJECT MATHS PERIODS

The pace of curriculum change in Ireland slowed after the 1976 revisions. However, in the 1980s and 1990s, further reviews led to introduction of revised curricula for the Intermediate Certificate (1987 – re-designated for the Junior Certificate in 1989), Leaving Certificate (1992) and Junior Certificate (2000). The rationale for and details of these revisions are described in a paper that is the source for material not otherwise referenced in this section (Oldham, 2007). The briefs for all three changes were limited, so the reviews were reactive rather than proactive: addressing perceived problems with implementation of their predecessors and with resulting student attainment, rather than rethinking mathematics education for the future – or indeed engaging deeply with either the back-to-the-basics approach or the subsequent focus on problem solving. However, it is relevant to note that the preambles or introductions again emphasised understanding and (to some extent) applications.

The effect of the changes was to greatly reduce the amount of material reflecting the Modern period. In terms of philosophy, the curricula were consciously eclectic: typical of the 1980s (Howson, 1991), but rather less so of the 1990s as the international community engaged with the Reform period. The Leaving Certificate Higher course, in particular, remained formal and abstract – *but* scarcely more so, if at all, than the curricula of the 1950s and earlier in dealing with traditional content: a point that has been overlooked in discussions of abstraction in Modern curricula. The legacy of the 1960s was reduced chiefly to the retention of some set theory (though no longer as an explicit foundation of as much content as possible); the presence of complex numbers, matrices and (as an option) groups, all treatable in a Modern spirit if teachers so chose; and continued use of Modern terminology and symbolism.

THE PROJECT MATHS STORY

The story of Project Maths has been well documented, for example in the comprehensive report by Shiel and Kelleher (2017): a source for otherwise unreferenced material in this section. A brief account suffices here. Dissatisfaction with student attainment sparked a critique by the National Council for Curriculum and Assessment (NCCA), beginning in 2002. The critique was eventually formalised in a discussion document (NCCA, 2005); circulation of the document, together with a questionnaire, to all post-primary schools initiated a consultation period with stakeholders. The NCCA also commissioned a research report on international trends in mathematics education, focusing on teaching, learning and assessment (Conway & Sloane, 2006) [2]. Thus, the context was set for beginning a substantial review.

Development of the revised curriculum took place over the next couple of years. At the *intended* level, it was envisaged that teaching and learning would emphasise, not only conceptual understanding, but also problem solving and applications set in real-life contexts – thus reflecting the Reform tradition – with State examinations mirroring those emphases. The eventual outcome was a curriculum innovation project introducing the revised curriculum on a phased basis. It began in 2008 in 24 schools (“Phase 1”), first involving only two out of five curriculum “strands” (“Probability and statistics” and “Geometry and trigonometry”); the strands “Number”, “Algebra” and “Functions” were introduced in Phase 1 schools over the following two years. Content changes included a further decrease in abstract algebra (groups, matrices and even vectors being eliminated) and also a reduction in calculus, both to accommodate extra probability and to allow time for constructivist learning. Implementation in all other schools followed the same pattern after a time-lag of two years. Atypically, the curriculum was introduced simultaneously into the first year of both junior and senior cycle.

For *implementation*, unusually extensive support for teachers addressed the intended philosophy and focused largely on pedagogy. It highlighted investigative approaches that had not previously taken root in a classroom culture which – despite all intentions – still featured over-emphasis on procedures (Oldham, 2001). A factor conducive to culture change was the altered style of examination papers, but the co-existence of older (including pre-Modern) and newer approaches, notably for algebra, was a confounding influence (Prendergast & Treacy, 2018). Overall, implementation was accompanied by animated discussions, written and oral, “pro” and “anti”: some based on the erroneous assumption that the outgoing curriculum content was still Modern and was intended to be taught without understanding (see note [2]).

Studies of *attainment* still reflect a curriculum in the process of implementation. However, there is anecdotal evidence of a decrease in procedural fluency: perhaps a result of general time pressures together with more focus on conceptual understanding and problem solving.

COMPARISONS AND CONTRASTS

Attention is now drawn to major comparisons and contrasts between the Modern Maths and Project Maths curricula, designated here for brevity as MM and PM respectively. The three curricular levels – intention, implementation and attainment – are considered in turn.

As regards *intention*, both MM and PM originated at system level, notably in response to international trends: the first constituting a rapid and maybe uncritical adoption of Modern

approaches (Oldham, 1980), the second involving a rather belated reaction to some twenty years of Reform-oriented debate. In contrast, the intervening revisions (with limited briefs) were driven more by national issues and teacher-generated pressure. Both MM and PM reflected identifiable philosophies of mathematics education, though these philosophies differ: that for MM being more static and absolutist, and that for PM being in a more dynamic tradition (Ernest, 2014) – neither, it may be said, uniformly popular with mathematicians. As noted, intervening revisions produced more eclectic curricula. Both PM and MM, like all curricula discussed here, strongly emphasised teaching for and learning with understanding; however, in the case of MM there was particular emphasis on mathematical coherence, while PM stressed student construction of meaning and benefited from evolution in theories of learning since the earlier period. The aims formulated for both MM and PM also made reference to applications, though in PM their role especially with regard to real-life contexts is very much greater. It is ironic that some of the Modern topics seen in the past as remote from student experience would be ripe for application in the era of the Internet.

For *implementation*, both reforms were introduced with considerable media publicity, and provoked discussion on a scale not experienced in the intervening period. Both MM and PM were phased in, albeit in notably different ways, allowing teachers to come to terms gradually with new content and approaches. In both cases, more professional development was provided than was usual at the time, though perhaps inevitably it was insufficient to overcome the challenge to teachers whose own explicit or tacit philosophies of mathematics education differed from those of the curricula. In both cases also, problems arose when older and newer content or approaches were combined in the curriculum: notably in MM for geometry and in PM for algebra. However, for PM – in contrast to the case for MM – intended change in classroom culture was supported by the radically altered style of State examination papers.

With respect to *attainment*, it is difficult to compare meaningfully across the fifty-year period. Proficiency naturally reflects curricular emphases at the time, and so change is inevitable. However, both MM and PM gave rise to perceptions of decreased procedural fluency, perhaps because such fluency does not result automatically from enhanced focus on understanding.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

The question posed in the title can now be answered: Modern Maths and Project Maths are indeed mirror images in many respects; moreover, since mirror images are laterally inverted, the metaphor can be extended to embrace the ways in which they are polar opposites. The similarities between the two, and their stories as told above, closely echo those observed for New Math and Reform curricula in the USA (Herrero & Owens, 2001). Telling the Irish stories has had two chief aims: first, historical accuracy, and secondly, lessons for the future.

The first aim was addressed by outlining the vision and excitement that accompanied introduction of the Modern Maths curricula and highlighting the extent to which these curricula (and indeed those succeeding them) were intended to promote *meaningful learning*. This is not to overlook the extent to which some aspects were mismatched to the student body, especially as the size of the participating cohort grew and included more learners whose strengths were not in the field of abstract study. The reformers of the Modern Maths era may

have been “incredibly naïve” in trying to bring about change in mathematics curricula and teaching without taking account of “complex institutional, political and cultural factors that shape school values and practices” (Fey, 2016, p. 422), but they were well intentioned. In fact, *all* changes discussed here reflected high ideals and were carried out with great care.

However, misinterpreting the goals of the Modern Maths period unintentionally masks the difficulty of introducing a curriculum based on a philosophy of mathematics education not widely shared by teachers, whose participation with conviction is so crucial in implementing official intentions, and indeed in moderating any that are intrinsically unworkable. When Modern curricula were taught by teachers who did not grasp – or who disagreed with – their underlying philosophy, teaching focused unduly on procedural fluency without developing conceptual understanding; analogously for Reform curricula, activities intended to facilitate construction of meaning can become hands-on but not minds-on busywork. Of note also is that abstraction and formalism did not start with the Modern period, but were features of mathematics education long before it. By over-identifying these features with a movement that – despite its virtues – was deemed to have failed (Herrero & Owens, 2001), we have minimised debate on where in mathematics education they have an appropriate place.

We are less naïve now than in the 1960s with regard to the challenges. Nonetheless, if we underestimate the difficulties experienced in changing classroom culture in the past, we may be paving the way for disappointment with regard to doing so in the future. If this paper helps in framing suitable discussion of the issues, its second aim will have been achieved.

NOTES

1. An assertion by Oldham (1980) that the courses represented the start of the “back to the basics” movement in Ireland was based on her incomplete understanding of that movement at the time.
2. This otherwise admirable book contains an error in attributing to the author (Oldham, 2001) the view that curricula at the time were still in the Modern tradition. The error has been replicated in several papers; some even suggest that Modern work was *intended* to be learnt without understanding. Oldham’s paper noted the *withdrawal* from most Modern content, and (of course) made no claim that procedural emphasis was “Modern”.

REFERENCES

- Conway, P., & Sloane, F. (2006). *International trends in post-primary mathematics education: Perspectives on learning, teaching and assessment*. Dublin, Ireland: National Council for Curriculum and Assessment.
- Department of Education (n.d. [1976]). *Rules and programme for secondary schools 1976/77*. Dublin, Ireland: Stationery Office.
- Ernest, P. (2014). What is mathematics, and why learn it? In P. Andrews & T. Rowland (Eds.), *MasterClass in mathematics education* (pp. 3–14). London, England: Bloomsbury.
- Fey, J. (2016). A review of the new math: A political history. *Journal for Research in Mathematics Education*, 47(4), 420–422.
- Herrera, T. A., & Owens, D. T. (2001). The “new new math”?: Two reform movements in mathematics education. *Theory into Practice*, 40(2), 84–92.

- Howson, G. (1991). *National curricula in mathematics*. Leicester, England: The Mathematical Association.
- Howson, G., Keitel, C., & Kilpatrick, J. (1981). *Curriculum development in mathematics*. Cambridge, England: Cambridge University Press.
- Lampiselkä, J., Ahtee, M., Pehkonen, E., Meri, M., & Eloranta, V. (2007). Mathematics and science in Finnish comprehensive school. In E. Pehkonen, M. Ahtee, & J. Lavonen (Eds.), *How Finns learn mathematics and science* (pp. 35–48). Rotterdam, Netherlands: Sense Publishers.
- Looney, A. (2014). Curriculum politics and practice: From “implementation” to “agency.” *Irish Teachers’ Journal*, 2(1), 7–14.
- National Council for Curriculum and Assessment. (2005). *Review of Mathematics in post-primary education: A discussion paper*. Dublin, Ireland: National Council for Curriculum and Assessment.
- Oldham, E. (1980). Post-primary mathematics in Ireland: An analysis of patterns in curriculum change. In D. J. Murphy & V. Rice (Eds.), *Mathematics, science and the gifted child: Conference proceedings and occasional papers* (pp. 49–59). Dublin, Ireland: Department of Higher Education and Research, Trinity College Dublin.
- Oldham, E. (2001). The culture of mathematics education in the Republic of Ireland: Keeping the faith? *Irish Educational Studies*, 20, 266–277.
- Oldham, E. (2007). A lot done, more to do? Changes in mathematics curriculum and assessment 1986-2006. In D. Corcoran & S. Breen (Eds.), *Second International Science and Mathematics Conference, Drumcondra, Dublin, September 2006* (pp. 161–174). Dublin, Ireland: Dublin City University.
- Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development. (1961). *New thinking in school mathematics*. Paris, France: Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development.
- Prendergast, M., & Treacy, P. (2018). Curriculum reform in Irish secondary schools – a focus on algebra. *Journal of Curriculum Studies*, 50(1), 126–143.
- Shiel, G., Cosgrove, J., Sofroniou, N., & Kelly, A. (2001). *Ready for life? The literacy achievements of Irish 15-year olds with comparative international data*. Dublin, Ireland: Educational Research Centre (ERC).
- Shiel, G., & Kelleher, C. (2017). *An evaluation of the impact of Project Maths on the performance of students in junior cycle mathematics*. Dublin, Ireland: ERC. Accessed at: [http://www.erc.ie/publications/evaluation-of-the-impact-of-project-maths-on-the-performance-of-students-in-junior-cycle-mathematics](#)
- Thompson, D. R., & Usiskin, Z. (Eds.). (2014). *Enacted mathematics curriculum: A conceptual framework and research needs*. Greenwich, CT: Information Age Publishing.
- Travers, K. J., & Westbury, I. (1989). *The IEA Study of Mathematics I: Analysis of mathematics curricula*. Oxford, England: Pergamon.
- Walmsley, A. L. E. (2007). *A history of mathematics education during the twentieth century*. Lanham, MD: University Press of America.